

DELIVERABLE 5.6 BROADENING PLAN ON EXTENSION CITY REGIONS

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20/12/2023

Funded
by the European Union

PROJECT ACRONYM:	FoodCLIC
PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER AND TITLE:	WP5 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation
LEAD BENEFICIARY:	ICLEI ES
WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	ICLEI ES
RELEVANT TASK:	5.3 Replication: finetuning and implementation of the broadening strategy (M16-54)
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU - Public
DUE DATE (MONTH):	16
VERSION:	1.0

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Anchoring and Broadening phase of the FoodCLIC project seeks to ensure the continuation of the policies, actions, and initiatives of the Food Policy Networks in FoodCLIC partner ('Pilot') cities and their Living Labs after project completion, as well as the broad dissemination of key findings and successes across Europe and beyond. An important part of this phase is the cross-learning with and dissemination of outputs in eight additional 'Broadening' city-regions, five in Europe and three in Africa. This Broadening Plan contributes to the scaling out of the FoodCLIC project by reaching new city-regions and geographies.

Innovating and testing new approaches, processes, and policies is an important step in **creating long lasting change in city-region food systems**. FoodCLIC works towards systemic change across food domains, geographies, and political scales. In order to understand the project's durability and resilience, we need to take action beyond the borders of the project's Living Labs (Aarhus, Amsterdam, Barcelona, Budapest, Brasov, Berlin, Lucca, Lisbon). The Pilot city-regions are collecting valuable experience in their Living Labs with new, and possibly challenging approaches, and experiences which they can share. These practical examples can provide input for other city-regions to adapt and test the FoodCLIC methodology to their specific contexts. At the same time, Broadening city-regions are discovering their own approaches and solutions to pressing food systems challenges. They are valuable new collaborators to exchange with to support cross-learning within the project on approaches, challenges, and best practices. Facilitating exchanges between existing Pilot city-region partners and Broadening city-regions is valuable to further develop the FoodCLIC project and processes by **identifying successful approaches in different contexts**. The goal is to go beyond providing information and towards enabling cities to take action by sharing tools, templates and processes, facilitating learning loops, and exploring synergies.

The Broadening Plan provides details on FoodCLIC's 'broadening process.' The process aims to facilitate the sharing, dialogue, translation and context-based adoption of good practices and lessons learned from FoodCLIC with the eight additional Broadening city-regions. This plan outlines the key steps to broaden the impact of the project and make its outputs relevant in different political, legal, institutional, socio-economic, and cultural contexts. **We understand broadening as identifying the specific features of a sustainable urban development approach (FoodCLIC process) that made it successful in a pilot setting (Living Lab food environment) and adapting them in another setting**, considering that the framework conditions and starting points could be quite different from those in the piloted city-region.

The ambition of working with Broadening city-regions is to support them in their efforts to develop science, policy and society connections for the purpose of food system transformation grounded in local action in city-region food environments. The Broadening city-regions will:

- draft a vision for their city-region food system;
- create or strengthen a Food Policy Network (FPN)/multi-stakeholder group focusing on food policy, initiatives, and activities;
- strengthen linkages with other city-regions;
- and support the development or implementation of a city-region food strategy integrated across scale (urban, peri-urban, rural) and sector (private, public, and civil society).

2. FOODCLIC'S BROADENING APPROACH

FoodCLIC's broadening approach is grounded in co-creation, a collaborative approach to engagement that allows stakeholders to develop inclusive and sustainable mechanisms for change.¹ FoodCLIC partners will provide a structure, tools, and templates, and remain responsive and open to adapting to the needs and requests of the Broadening city-regions. ICLEI European Secretariat (ES) will be the point of contact for the five European Broadening city-regions and ICLEI African Secretariat (AS) will be the point of contact for the three African city-regions. Together, ICLEI ES and AS will facilitate the implementation of this Broadening Plan.

A [call for participation](#) (discussed in detail in section 3. Becoming a FoodCLIC Broadening City-Region) was launched in November 2023 to select five additional European city-regions and three African city-regions to act as FoodCLIC's Broadening city-regions. Based on the timeline in section seven of this document, and information provided during the application process, as well as a post-selection survey, a tailored broadening work plan/timeline will be adapted for and with each Broadening city-region. The work plan will outline roles and responsibilities, key dates, and activities, all of which are expected to be completed no later than June 2026 (see section 7. Timeline).

The broadening activities and workshop series will be based on updated guidelines for Broadening city-regions (D1.5) expected to be available in April 2024 and on the ongoing development of D1.7 Online Toolkit. Co-organised workshops and peer-to-peer learning and exchange will be at the core of the broadening strategy, which will draw on the learning and experience of FoodCLIC's Living Labs, in addition to taking into account those of Broadening city-regions. **The first three of FoodCLIC's five-phase approach (see Figure 1. FoodCLIC Phases and Process) will be adapted for broadening activities taking place in Broadening city-regions** to create learning loops and opportunities for impactful city-region to city-region exchanges and partnerships.

¹ Morello, E; Mahmoud, I; Gulyurtlu, S; Boelman, V; Davis, H (2018). [CLEVER Cities Guidance on co-creating nature-based solutions: PART I - Defining the co-creation framework and stakeholder engagement](#). Deliverable 1.1.5, CLEVER Cities, H2020 grant no. 776604.

FoodCLIC's Think Tank has been tasked with strategic support for the development and overall guidance of the Anchoring and Broadening phase, as outlined in the Think Tank [Terms of Reference](#). The Think Tank, comprising of members with complementary thematic and geographic expertise in food systems - in addition to representing organisations with a global reach and network - will provide feedback on and input into the broadening work. They supported establishing the criteria for the selection of broadening city-regions and will advise on the selection of the eight Broadening city-regions.

Figure 1. FoodCLIC Phases and Process.

3. BECOMING A FOODCLIC BROADENING CITY-REGION

3.1 PROCESS

City-regions across Africa and Europe are eligible to apply through an [online form](#) that requires identifying a point of contact for the interactions with FoodCLIC. The call will be advertised via FoodCLIC’s communications channels, including targeted emails to potential Broadening city-regions by ICLEI, as well as by Think Tank, Stakeholder Advisory Board, and Consortium member networks. A selection committee consisting of ICLEI AS, ICLEI ES, and ICLEI World Secretariat (WS) will assess applications against [a set of transparent criteria](#) (see Annex A), published on the FoodCLIC website. The selection committee will ‘shortlist’ potential Broadening city-regions and seek input from FoodCLIC’s Think Tank and the project coordinator for the final selection. Selected City-regions will be asked to co-develop a work plan, based on section 6. Responsibilities and Benefits, with ICLEI ES, AS, and WS and sign a letter of commitment for participation (see Annex B). The identification and selection of the eight Broadening city-regions will take place in the first quarter of 2024 during the early stages of FoodCLIC’s Phase 5 ‘Anchoring and Broadening’ (according to the FoodCLIC Grant Agreement).

Process for becoming a FoodCLIC Broadening city-region (see Figure 2. Process for becoming a FoodCLIC Broadening city-region)²:

1. Interested city-regions apply using an online form.
2. Selection committee reviews applications and solicits input from the Think Tank and VU.
3. Selected Broadening city-regions sign Letter of Commitment.
4. Onboarding meeting between Broadening city-regions and ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS to establish a way of working, draft a context-based work plan and begin a pre-survey.
5. Work plan finalised.
6. Begin broadening activities (see section 5. Broadening Activities).

Figure 2: Process for becoming a FoodCLIC Broadening city-region.

² For a more detailed description of the activities, timelines and responsibilities see section 7. Timeline.

3.2 ELIGIBILITY AND CRITERIA

With an ambition to strengthen African and European city relations, and according to the project's grant agreement, applicants from an African or European country are encouraged to apply. The applicant must represent a geographical area that corresponds to OR is close to the concept of a city-region (urban centre, province, area, town, township or rural centre with a common governing body) and shows interest in strengthening rural-urban linkages and/or improving relationships between different territories and territorial levels. Synergies or conflicts arising from participating in other Horizon funded projects will also be considered. For the final selection, the political stability of the city(-region) will be taken into consideration (to ensure that the economic, cultural and environmental conditions of the city-region should enable the implementation of the project activities) and that cities themselves are committing to political neutrality (i.e., allow capacity-building across the political spectrum), thereby ensuring project continuity over the mid-term.

The full set of criteria is published online on the FoodCLIC website, [here](#)³ and in **Annex A**. Through the [online application form](#), city-regions applying to FoodCLIC's broadening activities will be asked to demonstrate, amongst other things:

- A clear intention to work on urban food governance, showing that urban food governance and transformation is a priority in their political agenda – for example, through the inclusion of food in existing strategies/ projections or existing initiatives.
- Interest in food system transformation and the relevance of FoodCLIC's process for the city-region, as evidenced by local/ urban, climate, environmental and social challenges, as well as by relevant strategies and activities across scales (local, regional, national).
- Commitment to, and political support for, working on food system issues and developing local food policies and/ or programs and initiation of some related activities (even if preliminary).
- Existing experience with and/ or the ability to mobilise food systems stakeholders across sectors present in the city-region (private, public, and academic) and across scales (local, regional, national).
- Status of or willingness to consider, where appropriate, creating a formal Food Policy Network (FPN), namely a multi-stakeholder body focusing on food system policies, activities, and initiatives.
- Capacity and willingness to dedicate appropriate staff time and engage with FoodCLIC to co-organise three local workshops/events based on FoodCLIC's process.
- Interest and willingness to engage in peer-to-peer learning activities and national and international events.
- Ability of city-region representatives to communicate in English as the project's primary working language.

³ Participation criteria: https://foodclic.eu/sites/default/files/media/images/documents/FoodCLIC%20Broadening%20-%20Selection%20Criteria_web.pdf.

4. BROADENING ACTIVITIES IN BROADENING CITY-REGIONS

Broadening city-regions will implement a portion of the FoodCLIC process. They will focus on steps 1 to 7 of the 10-step FoodCLIC process described below (see Figure 3. FoodCLIC Process). Broadening city-regions will conduct similar activities as the partner city-regions through step 7, identify pathways for change.

Figure 3. FoodCLIC Process.

Depending on the city-region's starting point and framework conditions, they may engage in work related to step 8, agree on priorities, actions, timelines, responsibilities, and resources. Broadening city-regions will receive support in the uptake and application of FoodCLIC's processes and resources. They will also engage in **FoodCLIC's monitoring process** (reflexive learning/journaling). This will both support their work and help refine and update FoodCLIC's guidelines, tools and models for wider application in the EU and beyond. A tailored broadening work plan (based on Section 7. Timeline) will specify broadening activities and a timeline in the broadening city-regions.

Through a series of workshops and peer-to-peer exchange, each Broadening city-region will be guided through the FoodCLIC process and framework for inclusive and sustainable food systems (see Figure 2. FoodCLIC Process). Workshops will be planned with Broadening city-regions in accordance with their existing needs, priorities and emerging opportunities. The workshop series will therefore differ slightly from one Broadening city-region to the other. As appropriate, training workshops will be set up for Broadening city-regions in collaboration between FoodCLIC partners, especially WPs 1 and 5 (for more information see section 6. Relevance for other FoodCLIC WPs).

The Broadening city-regions will have access to **tailored training packages** to address gaps, leverage opportunities, develop a vision, identify pathways for change and render planning frameworks food-sensitive across city-regions. The packages will include sample agendas and templates and process guides/ notes for the city-region workshop activities. Additionally, **support for peer-to-peer dialogues and exchange opportunities (see section 4. Broadening Activities in Broadening City-Regions)** will provide Broadening city-regions with opportunities to meet and exchange amongst themselves and with FoodCLIC's Pilot city-regions, both online and in-person.

At the end of the process, Broadening city-regions will have a **FoodCLIC Broadening Report for their city-region** (reinterpretation of the Grant Agreement's specified "situation analysis" report) that includes the necessary components to draft an integrated food strategy. The report will be co-written by the city-region focal point and ICLEI ES/ ICLEI AS in an iterative process based on the (planned) engagement activities in each city-region. The template for this report will be provided at the start of the broadening process. The report will include a section on the FoodCLIC broadening activities in the city-region, an assessment of gaps, needs, and topics for further learning and capacity building, a vision, and strategic pathways. This document will capture all the important information that emerged from the broadening and peer-to-peer processes and will/can be used to inform future food systems strategies/ policies and programmes or interventions in the respective city-region.

The FoodCLIC Broadening Reports for the city-regions will feed into two project progress reports that will be used to support the comparative analysis of the overall contribution of FoodCLIC's activities towards healthier, sustainable, and resilient food systems (D5.9 and D5.12).

4.1 FOODCLIC PROCESS

The FoodCLIC process is a step-wise approach based on the CLIC framework⁴. The following steps support city-regions in moving towards food system transformation (see Table 1. FoodCLIC step-by-step process).

Preparation (FoodCLIC phase 1)	Step 1: Secure commitment.
	Step 2: Develop a way of working together.
	Step 3: Stakeholder identification and mapping.
	Step 4: Establish co-creation with stakeholders.
Strategic Planning (FoodCLIC phases 2)	Step 5: Analyse the current state of the local food system (relevant to FoodCLIC (e.g., baseline assessment/needs and gaps/challenge analysis for at least one category of food environment ⁵).
	Step 6: Develop a long-term vision.
Strategic Planning contd. (FoodCLIC phase 3)	Step 7: Identify pathways for change.
	Step 8: Agree on priorities, actions, responsibilities, timelines, and resources.
Implementation and policy planning (FoodCLIC phase 4) (outside of scope of Broadening Plan)	Step 9: Put the plan into action.
Anchoring and Broadening (FoodCLIC phase 5) (outside of scope of Broadening Plan)	Step 10: Build relationships and connections with other city-regions to extend the impact of the FoodCLIC process.

Table 1. FoodCLIC step-by-step process.

⁴ The CLIC framework emphasises sustainability Co-benefits, spatial Linkages, social Inclusion, and sectoral Connectivity. More information is available on the [FoodCLIC website](https://www.foodcllic.eu).

⁵ Food environments include: Agri-food (e.g., home/ communal/ rooftop gardens; community-supported agriculture), Hospitality (restaurants, take-away shops, etc.), Retail (e.g. (super)markets), Community (e.g., food-consumer cooperatives), Institutional (e.g., public canteens, schools), Wild (edible landscaping, land left for nature)

4.2 WORKSHOP SERIES

The FoodCLIC process will primarily be executed through a workshop series and related activities co-designed by the Broadening city-regions and ICLEI ES/ ICLEI AS. The planned activities will be designed to include the following topics as appropriate:

Preparation (June 2024 - February 2025)

- **Step 1: Secure commitment** - Broadening city-regions provide documentation that they will be able to participate in the FoodCLIC project as described in this plan.
- **Step 2: Develop a way of working together** - Food system transformation requires working across boundaries and sectors, coordinating between related policies and organisations (e.g., political, educational, private sector, mobility, health etc.), and acknowledging different types of knowledge (scientific, experiential). Cross sectoral collaboration is essential to ensure coherence with existing activities. A clear point of contact with sufficient capacities to keep the FoodCLIC process moving forward is critical.
- **Step 3: Stakeholder identification and mapping** - Each Broadening city-region will perform an actor analysis and mobilise stakeholders to strengthen or develop the structure of a multi-stakeholder body for food initiatives (comprising practitioners from civil society and private parties, policymakers, planners, and researchers). Relevant insights, lessons learned and good practices from within FoodCLIC will be identified and analysed.
- **Step 4: Establish co-creation with stakeholders** - Engaging with and incorporating diverse perspectives, knowledge, and experiences of local stakeholders is vital to ensure the FoodCLIC process is relevant and can lead to future impact. A co-creation process is designed to fully engage key stakeholders in the FoodCLIC process (civil society groups, food deprived communities, academia, business community, relevant municipal departments).

Strategic Planning (January 2025 - August 2026)

- **Step 5: Analyse the current state of the local food system** - Building a joint understanding of the food environment and interrelated food systems in each city-region, including through the analysis of data (e.g., on consumer behaviour) and relevant existing and upcoming (local, regional and national) policies on food and adjacent policy-domains and planning developments (including newly planned or regeneration of urban areas).
- **Step 6: Develop a long-term vision** - Based on the shared understanding of baseline conditions, city-regions will develop a vision for the future, using the pillars of the CLIC framework and taking into account the needs and interests of stakeholders.
- **Step 7: Identify pathways for change** - Transformational capacity will continue to be built by reflecting on possible pathways and measures for change towards the envisaged urban food system and by discussing past successes, scrutinising failures and identifying relevant organisational and network capacities that can be mobilised.

4.2.1 ONLINE SUPPORT

Online support, communication, and guidance will be offered to Broadening city-regions by ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS. Additional FoodCLIC project partners will be involved based on needs and interests. To support Broadening city-regions in organising their activities, ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS will organise three joint webinars targeting topics such as:

- Mapping and baseline assessments
- Stakeholder engagement
- Inclusive and adaptive governance
- Visioning
- Strategy planning and pathway identification

4.3 MUTUAL LEARNING AND PEER-TO-PEER EXCHANGE

The aim of FoodCLIC's peer-to-peer exchanges is to facilitate cross-learning and learning loops, engage with FPNs and multi-stakeholder groups, assess the applicability of FoodCLIC's resources, and explore partnership opportunities. Peer-to-peer exchange and learning opportunities will be organised based on the needs and desires of Pilot and Broadening city-regions. Events may target practitioners, policymakers, researchers and businesses based in Broadening city-regions. Peer-to-peer learning opportunities will be explored to feed into existing programmes, strategic events and FoodCLIC project meetings and conferences. Peer-to-peer exchange opportunities will entail online and in person exchanges between Pilot city-regions and Broadening city-regions. The exchange will aim at fostering mutual learning and capacity building and may include, for example, twinning, sharing of materials, presentations by city-regions and/ or FoodCLIC project partners, peer briefings, focused peer learning in groups and/or interactive peer exchanges. The calendar of events for peer-to-peer activities will be created following a step-wise approach:

- Survey of city-regions to understand their interest, needs, and format preferences (ICLEI ES, AS, and WS in collaboration with WP1, WP3, and WP4)
- Mapping of in-person events where side events could be organised (ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS)
- Alignment with other FoodCLIC and Food 2030 Network⁶ activities (ICLEI ES, ICLEI AS and VU)

⁶ <https://food2030.eu/>

4.4 FINANCIAL SUPPORT

The Broadening city-region staff will be accompanied by FoodCLIC consortium members and supported through dialogue and peer-to-peer exchanges taking place online and in-person (e.g., during workshops and conferences and ad-hoc as needed). The Broadening city-regions will not receive any direct financial support, nor will they be financially compensated or covered for staff time. Financial support is however available to organise workshops and for city and FPN members to travel to and attend events.

4.4.1 BROADENING ACTIVITIES AND WORKSHOP SERIES

Broadening city-regions will receive financial support for organising FoodCLIC-related activities and a workshop series in their city-region and for travelling to and from peer-to-peer engagement events and FoodCLIC sponsored conferences. As stated previously, activities will be organised in each of the Broadening city-regions to 1) identify and mobilise stakeholders; 2) create a vision; and 3) strategic planning and identification of future pathways for action. Costs will be dispersed on a reimbursement basis (unless agreed upon otherwise in advance), must be previously approved by ICLEI AS and ICLEI ES respectively, and follow ICLEI's reimbursement process.

4.4.2 AFRICAN BROADENING CITY-REGIONS

City-regions in Africa may utilise up to 10,000 euros each to organise their workshop series. An additional **17,000 euros** is available to be allocated on a needs-basis across all three African city-regions to cover all the travel-, accommodation-, subsistence and other direct costs associated with the workshop series. An additional **7,500 euros** will be utilised to ensure there is continued local interaction taking place between the workshop series through activities such as domestic communications, hiring local actors to organise and support with mapping, workshops and stakeholder coordination in general etc.

4.4.3 EUROPEAN BROADENING CITY-REGIONS

Broadening city-regions in Europe may access up to 25,000 euros to organise their FoodCLIC related activities and workshop series.

4.4.4 PEER-TO-PEER EXCHANGE AND TRAVEL

One to two persons per Broadening city-region are expected to participate in at least two in-person peer-to-peer learning activities and to attend FoodCLIC-sponsored activities, such as workshops, African and Latin American dissemination activities, the mid-term, and the final international conferences.

Broadening city-regions located in Europe may receive up to **3,300 euros per city-region** to support travel to and from FoodCLIC peer-to-peer learning activities and speaking/engagement opportunities.

Broadening city-regions located in Africa may receive up to **4,000 euros per city-region** to support travel to and from FoodCLIC peer-to-peer learning activities and speaking/engagement opportunities at strategic events.

ICLEI ES/ ICLEI AS will do their best to distribute the available budget fairly among the future Broadening city-regions. Taking into account the geographical location, the aim is to ensure that both African and European cities can participate equally (to the same extent) in in-person activities that require travelling.

All travel costs will be dispersed on a reimbursement basis and must be previously approved by ICLEI AS and ICLEI ES respectively and must follow an agreed upon reimbursement procedure. Where applicable, ICLEI AS will enter into a purchasing agreement with African Broadening city-regions for travel.

5. RELEVANCE FOR OTHER FOODCLIC WORK PACKAGES

This section articulates the relevance and connections between broadening activities and other FoodCLIC work packages. The table below (Table 2) highlights project’s deliverables of relevance to the Broadening work in broadening city-regions.

TIMELINE	DELIVERABLE	RESPONSIBLE	RELEVANCE
January 2024	D5.5 Short report on most valid food-related exploitation schemes	Cariplo	Background knowledge for D5.9 and D5.12 on potential financial streams for the implementation of integrated food policies
April 2024	D1.5 Updated guidelines for the extension city-regions in WP5	ICS-ULisboa	Guidelines for implementation of broadening process and workshops
May 2024	D1.4 Collated Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation Framework	VU	Background knowledge for reflexive monitoring in Broadening city-regions
November 2026	D4.4 Report on the comparative analysis of the Living Labs	Surrey	Information gathered in two progress reports will feed into D4.4
February 2027	D1.7 Online toolkit - guidelines and tools for mappings, real-life interventions, RMDE framework and training	VU	The ongoing development of this toolkit will be used by and refined in collaboration with Broadening city-regions

February 2027	D4.5 Set of guidelines, tools and policy recommendations	Surrey	Broadening activities will be considered in the development of D4.5 as stated above
February 2027	D6.3 Final report on processes and outcomes of the project	All	Broadening activities will be reported on in the final report on FoodCLIC project outcomes

Table 2. Project’s deliverables of relevance to the broadening work in Broadening city-regions.

5.1 WORK PACKAGE 1

WP1 will provide training materials for researchers, policymakers and practitioners and organise training workshops for coordinators and researchers of the Pilot city-region Living Labs (during M1-20). The scripts for these workshops will be made available to ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS for use with the Broadening city-regions. As appropriate, and on a need’s basis, ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS will use these materials collaboratively with WP1 and Pilot city-regions in face-to-face or online workshops to support Broadening city-regions in meeting their objectives.

D1.5 Updated guidelines for the extension city-regions in WP5 (ICS-ULisboa, Month 24) and D1.6 Guidelines and tools for the real-life interventions (VU, Month 26) will provide the foundation for the training packages for Broadening city-regions. WP5 partners will provide input into these deliverables from WP1 and WP4 by April 2024.

Upon reflection on the FoodCLIC process, input from WP leaders, and Pilot city-region Living Lab representatives, WP1 and WP5 agreed that a non-hierarchical relationship between city-regions was preferable. Therefore, the initially planned process of Pilot (Living Lab) city-regions training the Broadening city-regions has been re-interpreted and redefined in terms of a self-learning training package, which will also include templates, materials, and toolkits. ICLEI ES and ICLEI AS, with support from WP1, will provide Broadening city-regions with guidance on the use of materials in the form of ad-hoc meetings and according to the timeline in section. Pilot city-regions and Broadening city-regions will engage in peer-to-peer exchanges as described in section four (Broadening Activities in Broadening city-regions).

- D1.5 'updated guidelines for the extension city-regions in WP5' (ICS-ULisboa, M24) will include templates, scripts, sample agendas, definitions of key terms and self-learning materials.
- D1.7 'Online toolkit - guidelines and tools for mappings, real-life interventions, RMDE framework and training' (VU, M54) will include audio-visual materials (infographics, webinars, podcasts, vlogs etc.)

Timeline Work Package 1:

- WP1 will share drafts of updated guidelines for input and review by WP5 no later than April 2024.
- WP1 and WP5 will collaborate on D1.7 (VU) in order to align with example materials from WP3, D4.5, this Broadening Plan and the needs of Broadening city-regions.

5.2 WORK PACKAGE 3

WP3 works with the Pilot city-regions on co-designing and implementing integrated food policies and planning frameworks and real-life interventions. Example materials from this work package and the Pilot Living Labs will inform the self-learning training packages used in the broadening work. Opportunities to engage in workshops open to the public will be offered to Broadening city-regions.

Timeline Work Package 3:

- WP3 (HUB) will upload materials to share that may be of relevance to this Broadening Plan to a designated shared folder on an ongoing basis.

5.3 WORK PACKAGE 4

WP4 will synthesise policy-related research and outcomes into a set of guidelines, tools and recommendations for local/ sub-national, national and European policymakers, FPNs as well as other relevant food system actors (D4.5). By developing user-scenarios to identify key-users of the project's findings and understand their context, possibilities, and limitations, FoodCLIC will ensure that the outputs are in line with users' needs. The guidelines, tools and recommendations will be strategically promoted through FoodCLIC's dissemination activities (T5.2), embedded into the training/ self-learning package (T5.3) and uploaded to the Knowledge Hub.

- D4.4 Report on the comparative analysis of the Living Labs (HUB, M51) will include the eight Broadening city-regions and be discussed during the final international conference (organised by WP5 in 2026). WP4 and WP5 will collaborate on the format and timeline for exchanging information and contributing to D4.4 (ICLEI WS and HUB).

- D4.5 Set of guidelines, tools and policy recommendations (SURREY, M54). Will include input, experiences and needs of the Broadening city-regions.

Timeline Work Package 4:

- HUB and ICLEI WS will work together to align on formats and outcomes for D4.4.
- SURREY, Cariplo and VU will develop a timeline that aligns with D1.7, this Broadening Plan and the needs of Broadening city-regions for D4.5 (SURREY).

5.4 WORK PACKAGE 5

WP5 is responsible for communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the FoodCLIC project. Broadening activities, including peer-to-peer exchanges, will be highlighted in communication and dissemination events. The FoodCLIC process will also be considered as an exploitable result of the project. Additionally, WP5 partners have the budget and opportunity to send city officials and members of FPNs in Broadening city-regions to events and a wide range of peer-to-peer learning opportunities across the globe. Furthermore, a series of dissemination events will be organised by ICLEI AS, ICLEI ES, ICLEI WS and Metropolis to share the Broadening city-regions' stories. These dissemination events are also central to the peer-to-peer exchange and learning process of the broadening phase of the FoodCLIC project.

6. RESPONSIBILITIES AND BENEFITS

The table below (Table 3) describes the responsibilities and benefits of Broadening city-regions in the FoodCLIC project.

RESPONSIBILITIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fill-in application form to participate as a FoodCLIC Broadening city-region. ● Secure commitment for FoodCLIC broadening (collaboration with the FoodCLIC project). ● Co-develop a work plan with ICLEI AS and ICLEI ES. ● Organise a workshop series and/or related activities between June 2024 - June 2026. ● Provide input on (and data for) two status reports (FoodCLIC project deliverables) via templates and forms provided. ● Designate at least one point of contact for ongoing communication and for specific activities, attributing roles, and resources to carry out the project's activities. ● Allow city staff (e.g., point of contact) to take part in relevant opportunities, including peer-to-peer exchanges and conferences, etc. ● Participate in peer-to-peer learning activities and attend at least two FoodCLIC-sponsored activities, such as workshops, African and Latin American dissemination activities, the mid-term, and the final international conferences. ● Co-write/ contribute to the FoodCLIC Broadening Report for the city-region. ● By July 2026, develop localised food-systems strategic pathways for change, grounded in the FoodCLIC framework.
BENEFITS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Co-adapted training packages, guidance materials, tools and strategic support based on FoodCLIC's findings and achievements. ● Networking and peer-to-peer exchange opportunities with project cities, consortium partners, and knowledge experts. ● Travel budgets to attend FoodCLIC-sponsored activities and financial support for the logistical organisation of three workshops (room and catering). ● Global visibility and opportunity to promote local solutions. ● FoodCLIC Broadening Report for the city-region that can be used as a baseline for developing food systems strategies and interventions based on co-identified pathways of change.

Table 3. Responsibilities and benefits for Broadening city-regions.

7. TIMELINE

This section provides an overview of broadening related activities, timeline, and responsible parties (see Table 4. Broadening related activities).

	Timeline	Action	Responsible	Comments
Selecting	March 15 th 2024	Apply as a Broadening city-region	Broadening city-region	
	March 27 th 2024	Review meeting to select Broadening city-region shortlist, send shortlist to TT and VU on 28th	ICLEI AS, ES, WS	ICLEI Internal
	April 2024	Input on Broadening city-regions shortlist from Think Tank and VU	ICLEI WS / ICLEI ES	WS to look for date for 2nd TT Meeting
	April 15 th 2024	Inform selected city-regions	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	One email sent from both organisations
	April 30 2024	Confirm selection of Broadening city-regions, and a following signed letter of commitment (MS22)	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	Due Month 18 Changed to M20
Broadening	May 2024	Online welcome and onboarding meeting for all Broadening city-regions	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS / ICLEI WS	Send pre-survey, which informs the work plan, plan for peer-to-peer activities, and FoodCLIC Broadening Report
	July 2024	Tailored broadening work plans complete and beginning to develop the FoodCLIC Broadening Report for each Broadening city-region with timelines.	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	ICLEI ES and AS draft a work plan based on the survey/ questionnaire and send it to the city-regions to add details and begin the report

The table continues on the next page.

Broadening	Oct. 2024	Peer-to-peer exchange event and workshop 1 preparation/training (online or in person)	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	Tentatively scheduled to be in-person at the FoodCLIC Consortium meeting and international workshop
	Dec. 2024 – April 2025	Mapping: 1st Broadening workshop/activities in each Broadening city-region, focus on mapping and gapping	Broadening city-region	
	Feb. 2025 Delay to May 2025	D5.9 Learnings and Progress Report #1	ICLEI WS	
	May/June 2025	Online peer-to-peer event and webinar/training for workshops 2 and 3 (visioning and strategy)	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	
	June/July 2025 - June 2026	Visioning and Planning: 2nd and 3rd workshops (visioning and strategy) in each Broadening city-region + online peer-to-peer event and webinar workshops	Broadening city-region	
	2026	2 of 2 in person peer-to-peer exchange events (Barcelona conference)	ICLEI ES / ICLEI AS	
	August 2026	D5.12 Learnings and Progress Report #2	ICLEI WS	

Table 4. Broadening related activities.

8. ANNEX

8.1 ANNEX A: BROADENING-CITY SELECTION CRITERIA

Please see the following pages.

FOODCLIC BROADENING CALL FOR PARTICIPATION - SELECTION CRITERIA

November 2023

Funded
by the European Union

FOODCLIC BROADENING - SELECTION CRITERIA

SECTION #1	CRITERIA	ELIGIBILITY CHECK: YES/ NO
Fundamental requirements	The applicant is located in an African country, in a European Union <u>Member State</u> or in a <u>country associated to Horizon Europe</u> (e.g. acceding, candidate, and potential candidate).	Yes / No
	The applicant represents a geographical area that corresponds to OR is close to the concept of a city-region (urban centre, province, area, town, township or rural centre with a common governing body). AND/ OR The applicant shows interest in strengthening rural-urban linkages and/or improving relationships between different territories and territorial levels.	Yes / No
	There is no conflict of interest and/or conflict arising from participation in other Horizon funded projects.	Yes / No
	Political stability and commitment to political neutrality were considered and are assumed.	Yes / No
	The application has been submitted electronically via the form provided on the EUSurvey service platform .	Yes / No
	The application form is filled in English and is clearly understandable.	Yes / No

	The applicant has sufficiently answered/filled in all questions/fields of section 1 of the application form.	Yes / No
	The applicant has sufficiently answered/filled in all questions/fields of section 2 of the application form.	Yes / No
SECTION #2	CRITERIA	ELIGIBILITY CHECK: SCORE (1 (LOW) TO 5 (HIGH))
	The applicant shows sufficient interest in activities carried out in the framework of the project and in the role of a Broadening city-region.	1 – 5
	The applicant shows a clear intention to work on (urban) food-related policy, governance and/or transformation.	1 – 5
	The applicant identifies local/ urban challenges relevant to the FoodCLIC process.	1 – 5
	According to the applicant's understanding and answers, there is political support for working on food system issues in general, for developing local food policies and/or programmes and for initiating food system transformation activities.	1 – 5
	Appropriate attention is given to areas of the local food system relevant for FoodCLIC (Agri-food (e.g. home/ communal/ rooftop gardens; community-supported agriculture), Hospitality (restaurants, take-away shops, etc.), Retail (e.g. (super)markets), Community (e.g. food-consumer cooperatives), Institutional (e.g. public canteens,	1 – 5

	schools), Wild (edible landscaping, land left for nature) or others)	
	The candidate has experience in, or capacity to, engage stakeholders across sectors (private, public, academic) and scales (local, regional, national) that are active in food systems transformation.	1 – 5
	The applicant knows (and is maybe in contact with) organisations, networks or other groups that deal with the topic of food system(s) transformation/ are engaged in the food environment.	1 – 5
	The applicant pays (special) attention to vulnerable or food-deprived groups and demonstrates that respective policies are in place / measures are taken OR the applicant indicates that there is room for improvement to establish inclusive policies and initiatives.	1 – 5
	The applicant confirms that he/she will actively participate in the FoodCLIC project and related activities, mainly at his/her own expense (staff time).	1 – 5
	The applicant has experience in using English as a primary working language.	1 – 5

WE LOOK FORWARD TO RECEIVING YOUR APPLICATION!
IF YOU HAVE ANY QUESTIONS, PLEASE DO NOT HESITATE TO CONTACT US:
 Email: foodclic.beta@vu.nl

8.2 ANNEX B: DRAFT LETTER OF COMMITMENT

LETTER OF COMMITMENT FoodCLIC BROADENING CITY REGIONS

This letter serves as a formal commitment by the city-region of **NAME OF THE CITY-REGION** to participate in the FoodCLIC project as a Broadening city-region from **DD.MM.2024** until the end of the project. **NAME OF THE CITY-REGION** will be responsible for (i) appointing one or more representatives who will fulfil the project activities mentioned in the FoodCLIC Broadening Plan, following the process described in the plan; (ii) co-writing the FoodCLIC Broadening Report for the city-region; and (iii) participating in bilateral meetings with ICLEI- (*frequency to be added at the time of signing*), in the peer-to-peer exchange; (iv) attending international events; and (v) co-organising a workshop series by the end of June 2026.

The city-region of **NAME OF THE CITY-REGION** understands that, in order to achieve the above-mentioned aims, it will receive from the FoodCLIC project the following:

- Adapted training packages, guidance materials and tools developed in the framework of the FoodCLIC project.
- Knowledge sharing, networking and peer-to-peer exchange opportunities with project city-regions, consortium partners, and knowledge experts.
- Up to 3,300 EUR for EU/4,000 EUR for Africa EUR financial support to cover travelling expenses to attend FoodCLIC-sponsored activities. *For Africa: ICLEI AS may enter into a purchasing agreement with broadening city-regions.*
- Up to 25,000 EUR for EU/10,000 EUR for Africa financial support to organise a workshop series (est. three workshops) in terms of content communication and logistics.

This agreement is not binding and has the sole purpose to clarify the nature of the involvement of **NAME LOCAL GOVERNMENT** in the FoodCLIC broadening activities. No party shall be entitled to act or make legally binding declarations on behalf of the other Parties. This agreement remains valid until the end of the FoodCLIC project unless either party terminates in writing stating its reasons for interrupting the commitment.

Any personal data provided during our cooperation with the FoodCLIC consortium will be treated confidentially for the exclusive use of the FoodCLIC project in accordance with the provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/779/EU – GDPR).

NAME LOCAL GOVERNMENT's Representative agrees and acknowledges what is written on this letter by signing below.

Signature: _____

Full name: _____ Position within the organisation: _____

Date: _____

PARTNERS

CONTACT US

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